

CONTENT AND MAIN CHARACTERISTICS OF SOCIAL COOPERATION

Shodmonova D. Shakhnoza

Researcher of Fergana State University,
Fergana, Uzbekistan

e-mail: alfargoniy.uz@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13329026>

Annotation: in this article, within the framework of the topic, aspects revealing the essence and main features of social cooperation, as well as the essence and main features are analyzed.

Key words: social relations, consensus of social conflicts, social consensus, ideological threats, ideological threats.

Within the framework of the topic, we pay attention to aspects that reveal the essence and main features of social cooperation. We would like to put forward several scientific hypotheses.

1. State initiative plays a major role in the development of social cooperation. It is known that the state has a great role in the sustainable development of the society, the realization of strategic goals and tasks, and the activation of its mechanism. After all, one of the important principles of the transition to a market economy in Uzbekistan is that the state is the main reformer. Based on this principle, it should be noted that the state organizes, coordinates and controls social cooperation relations, intervenes in society's affairs within the framework of the law, creates the necessary conditions, and ensures that the principles of social justice are not violated. Also, the state plays a special role in organizing social cooperation activities, providing sufficient funds, protecting the rights of cooperative entities, and strengthening the legal foundations of cooperative farms and business entities. Naturally, in the process of economic liberalization and modernization, the contribution of the state in determining measures to encourage the interaction of joint ventures, associations, and firms operating on the basis of social partnership, providing them with all-round support, rational use of existing resources, and the implementation of various incentives and technologies is incomparable.

2. Social cooperation is firmly established only in the conditions of civil society. It is not an exaggeration to say that the strategic goal of building a democratic state and civil society, which has been set in our country since the first days of independence, is directly and indirectly based on the unity and mutual cooperation of our citizens, the nation and the people. An important

condition for the development of civil society is mutual balance, social cooperation, equality between the state, society and the individual. In this sense, thinkers of all times tried to justify this idea.

According to the Greek philosopher Plato, "the main purpose of people's joining and participation in society is to achieve prosperity and stability." Also, the philosopher continues his opinion in his work "Law" and says: "State building has two children like a mother. We will not make a mistake if we refer to the first as absolute rule and the second as democracy. The rest are legally born from them. Absolute rule (monarchy) in the Persians, and democracy in our country. All other types of state building, as I mentioned, consist of a colorful and soft combination of these two. In order for freedom and friendship to co-exist (live) with consciousness, it must necessarily belong to this species. A state that does not belong to them will not have a good order (construction)" [1].

In fact, the essence of civil society, the process of its formation, views on peaceful and peaceful living of people have been thoroughly studied by Eastern and Western thinkers. "Virtuous society" (Faroabi), "correct and just government" (Confucius), "ideal and just society" (Socrates and Plato), "just and fair ruler" (Nizamulmulk), "ahli ma'ni", "ahli suvrat" (Alisher Navoi), "power is in justice" (Amir Temur), "social contract" or "community of patriots" (J.J. Rousseau), "general legal civil society" (I. Kant) are among them. In all these interpretations, the unique aspects and characteristics of civil society are embodied, and it can be observed that principles such as diversity of opinions, freedom of social life, inviolability of private life, legality, and social justice are harmonious in the activities of people based on mutual solidarity. We believe that the following generalized analytical conclusions of sociologists about civil society will further clarify its essence: firstly, community life is a human unity formed voluntarily in the economic, social and spiritual spheres of activity, including primary non-state systems; secondly, it is a complex of economic, social, family, national, spiritual, moral, religious, production, personal and non-state relations in society; thirdly, it is a society where free individuals, voluntarily formed organizations and various bodies of citizens are protected by laws from oppression, interference or homogenization, in which they have a constant opportunity to express themselves [2].

3. Cooperation requires social responsibility. The aspect of the issue that we are analyzing is also related to the problem of human freedom. It is known that, despite the fact that any person is free to choose the method of action towards the achievement of the goal that is important to him, his personal life is

inextricably linked with the life of the whole society and responsibility towards others. Society, for its own preservation and development, has to form a certain internal order and practically limit the inappropriate actions of its members. Thus, people's will and responsibility are inextricably linked with behavioral standards. Such a situation is manifested in the fact that all members of society consciously accept certain obligations to each other and society, as well as in their readiness to fulfill them in necessary cases.

It is known from history that society cannot progress consistently if all branches of government are not stable and responsible. This issue is gaining importance in today's world. When social responsibility is defined as a category of morality and law, it reflects a special social and moral-legal attitude of a person to society, following his moral duty and legal norms. In this context, responsibility is the level of understanding of the interests and cooperation of the state and society in making management decisions.

In some works, social responsibility is the form of social control over personal behavior, ultimately, the intended goal, the criteria of compliance of the political, legal, social and other relations of the subject of management with the object, the ability to answer to the organization, the state and society for the work performed, the leader's professional , is defined as a factor of personal and business qualities, his style of activity, management motivation and his efficiency [3,4]. So, today, in the process of democratic development and development of civil society in our country, social cooperation is a guarantee of increasing social responsibility in society.

The formation of a new legal environment in the establishment and development of social partnership in the society is the basis for the creation of specific conditions for strengthening the social cooperation of citizens. In turn, the social status of citizens, economic stability, and the effectiveness of their activities in private production are determined by social stability. The social stability of society includes a set of organizational methods, methods and attitudes. The state supports small business by creating a social system guarantee, protects the rights of entrepreneurs and owners, as well as customers. Market relations require the activation of the activities of the subjects of social control, ensuring that a person receives income in legal ways. Today, social issues, like other fields and areas, are recognized among the urgent issues that are waiting for their solution. From this point of view, in order to create unique forms of social cooperation in the society, it is necessary for citizens to unite socially and engage in social cooperation. It should be noted

that the opinion and interests of the majority in civil society determine the position of the society. Also, achieving social stability in the society today requires paying special attention to issues of social cooperation among citizens.

It has its own aspects, and social cooperation is manifested in the development of economic, political, cultural, ideological directions with its important features.

Social cooperation plays an important role in identifying and eliminating social conflicts in the life of the society. From this point of view, social cooperation can be recognized as an important aspect of peace and reconciliation, elimination of tension in society.

In this process, the creation of a legal basis for social cooperation is an important factor for the rise of civil society institutions and their importance in the life of our society. Also, social cooperation makes it possible to ensure the transparency of the reforms implemented in society today and for each member of society to understand them correctly with the support of civil society institutions and social partners.

In conclusion, taking into account that the way of life and well-being of citizens depends on the quality and effectiveness of the reforms implemented in the country, it is appropriate to create legal, organizational, moral, educational and economic bases for establishing social cooperation.

References:

1. Plato. Laws. Translation from Russian by Urfon Otajon. - T.: New age generation, 2002. - B.95.
2. Rakhmanov A.R. Civil society: achievements, problems, prospects.. Study guide - Tashkent: Akademiya, 2007
3. Problems of social responsibility in the complex of global problems of our time // Scientific review. V.E. Ermolova. - M., 1987;
4. Social responsibility of scientists in the ideological struggle. // Collection of articles -1989; Sayan A.K. Social responsibility: concepts, types, genesis, grounds. Abstract of candidate of law. - Yerevan, 2002; Dorofeev E.D. Intra-group responsibility in the context of joint activities. Abstract of candidate of philosophical sciences. - M.: RAGS, 1994.
5. <https://soglom.uz/archives/> Ashurova G. Ideological threat: we no longer defend, but fight back
6. Yakaslikov J.Ya., Muhammadiev N.E. National idea - development strategy. - Tashkent: Science, 2017. - B. 316.
7. Otamuratov S. Globalization and national moral security. - Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 2013. - B. 259.

POLAND

CURRENT APPROACHES AND NEW RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCES

International scientific-online conference

POLAND

8. Jamolov L. Globalization and spiritual threats // Collection of materials of the republican scientific-practical conference "Spiritual-educational technologies of patriotic education in the conditions of globalization". - Tashkent: 2019. - B. 25.
9. Ramatov J.S., Rakhimova M.I., Hasanov M.N. The role of Islamic values in preventing ideological threats. Academic Research in Educational Sciences Volume 3 | Issue 6 | 2022. - B. 1033. https://t.me/ares_uz
10. Ramatov J.S., Rakhimova M.I., Hasanov M.N. The role of Islamic values in preventing ideological threats. Academic Research in Educational Sciences Volume 3 | Issue 6 | 2022. - B. 1034. https://t.me/ares_uz

